

UPWARDS

Deliverable D6.3

HPC for Integrated Simulation Platform

WP	6	Integrated System Simulation and Knowledge Extraction
Task	6.3	HPC- Integrated Simulation Environment implemented and tested

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Deliverable abstract

This document reports about the **HPC extended Simulation Platform**, which was implemented in Task 6.3. Here, the simulation tools and models developed in WP2-WP5 are coupled and executed by HPC method.

Deliverable Review

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1. Is the deliverable in accordance with

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² Nature of the deliverable: **R** = Report. **P** = Prototype. **D** = Demonstrator. **O** = Other

³ Creation, modification, final version for evaluation, revised version following evaluation, final

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1. Introduction

Deliverable D6.3 describes the extended design and usage of the *Integrated Simulation Platform*, which was developed in Task 6.1, and extended in Task 6.3. The goal to reach in Task 6.3 is to execute wind park simulations in parallel on an HPC cluster environment like the Fraunhofer ITWM HPC cluster Beehive.

In detail the objective of Task 6.3 was to refine the Upwards *Serial Integrated Simulation Platform*, which we delivered in D6.1, to allow multiple parallelized execution of the software systems used to perform physical simulations on wind parks and turbines. This runtime environment platform couples and executes these simulation systems in a standardized workflow and finally provides an overall insight of high-fidelity simulation results related to the atmospheric states at a wind park location, the flow fields within a wind park, the states of each turbine and blades, and the noise fields generated by turbines. The platform allows users:

- to pass configurations to simulators, such as initial conditions and model parameters.
- to execute systems within a workflow step on multiple core compute nodes.
- to pass results from one simulation system as input to another simulation system.
- to represent simulation results in data format which allows further data analytics.

Extending results of Task 6.1 the aim of Task 6.3 was to refactor and extend the runtime that way, that multiple compute nodes and cores of ITWM cluster Beehive can be involved in parallel. This effort allows users to reduce the response time for computing simulation results. Still, we preserved the open access interface (see Figure 1) which was intended in the Upwards proposal to link all the software simulation tools developed in UPWARDS in one integrated framework. These open access interface allows partners to:

- replace each tool by third party products when considering the application interfaces and
- have the capability to linked additional tools.

To that end, and not to interfere with the partners' IPR, the source code of each partner will not be open access, but an application interface to initialize and run the simulation will be provided, with guidelines on how to use it and which will be open.

Figure 1: OPEN INTERFACE Simulation Framework

Figure 2 gives an overview about the concept and design of Upwards. This deliverable focuses on the model layer and implements a parallelizable version of the workflow to execute simulations.

Figure 2: Design of Upwards simulation framework.

1.1. Contributions to project objectives

The concept underpinning UPWARDS is to develop an integrated HPC simulation framework of high-fidelity simulation codes capable of performing high fidelity wind turbine and wind energy park simulations including wind flow, fully coupled fluid structure interaction, progressive damage, and noise propagation

The implementation of this HPC integrated simulation platform contributes to the project objectives of the Upwards agreement:

Objective 1:

Establish a high-fidelity multi-physics, mechatronic and multi-scale simulation framework for wind turbines that enables integrated modelling of wind flow, mechanical movements, structural/control dynamics, and stresses with a level of details that today only is achievable in modelling of isolated phenomena.

- b) State of the simulation tools and models for wind flow from atmospheric to turbine scale, rotor noise generation and propagation and composite material damage models. Methods and protocols will be developed to link these tools to enable efficient sequential modelling of all scales and physics.

Objective 3:

Generate in-depth knowledge of important wind turbine related physical phenomena through high fidelity simulations.

- a) High fidelity simulations of important wind turbine related phenomena will be performed using the high-fidelity simulation framework described in Objective 1 to exploit and increase the understanding of their physical behaviour and interaction.

Objective 5:

Distribute and enable further use of the generated knowledge, data, and results

- e) HPC Simulation Interface linking different type of simulation tools and models

1.2. Document Outline

This documentation provides explanation to all components used to implement the HPC Integrated Simulation Platform:

Section 2

- The workflow to combine physical simulation systems
- The models and parameters that are involved in this workflow
- The systems that use these models to simulate physical behaviours

Section 3

- The technical foundations to encapsulate systems in software containers
- The application interface to initialize and run the simulation on HPC clusters
- The data exchange interfaces in between systems

Section 4

- An explanation on how to use the system to generate simulation results.

Section 5

- Conclusion and outlook to use this HPC Integrated Simulation Platform within case studies in Task 6.6 And Task 7.3

Partners of the Upwards consortium access the platform by using the Gitlab collaboration platform hosted by Fraunhofer ITWM (<https://gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de/sys/upwards>).

2. The Upwards workflow connects physical simulation models

Figure 3 summarizes the workflow of Upwards high fidelity wind park simulation.

Figure 3: Upward's wind park simulation workflow

1. Starting from the geo location of a planned wind park, the **atmospheric model** simulates spatial and temporal wind conditions (velocity, direction, pressure) on atmospheric scale. The partner UL provides a tailored version of the LES-simulation system WRF^4 (Weather Research and Forecast Model).
2. Based on these wind conditions and based on a preconfigured set of wind turbines within the wind park, the **park model** simulates wind conditions on park and neighborhood scale in between the wind turbines in terms of turbulent flow fields (3D velocity vectors, 3D pressure). The partner SINTEF provides the simulation system `OpenFoam`⁵ with specialized solvers and models for this workflow step.
3. Based on the inflow conditions around each turbine, the **fluid-structure (Aeroelastic) interaction analysis** simulates the wind forces attacking the structural components (e.g., blades, shaft, and tower) of the turbine. The forces accumulate to progressive composite structure damage models. The partners SAMTECH, UNL, SISW, AaU, SINTEF, and SWP provide a coupled software stack consisting of `STAR-CCM+`⁶ (Wind 3D CFD model) and `SAMCEF`⁷ (Wind Turbine 3D non-linear Finite Element Analysis model, including kinematics and control), to achieve these simulations.
4. Based on the global and local inflow conditions of the park and around each turbine the partners IVKDF and SISW simulate **noise propagation** in terms of noise levels by Empirical

⁴ <https://www.mmm.ucar.edu/weather-research-and-forecasting-model>

⁵ <https://www.openfoam.com/>

⁶ <https://www.plm.automation.siemens.com/global/de/products/simcenter/STAR-CCM.html>

⁷ <https://www.plm.automation.siemens.com/global/en/products/simcenter/>

models for noise production coupled with ray-tracing atmospheric propagation model. They provide a software stack, which also incorporates among other software tools `STAR-CCM+` to reach this goal.

To summarize, Upwards' HPC enabled and integrated simulation system executes a workflow, which connects four models (i.e., atmospheric, park, fluid structure interaction, and noise) with respective software systems.

3. Technical foundations of the HPC Integrated Simulation framework

The implementation of the HPC integrated simulation system can be summarized as follows:

- At Fraunhofer ITWM, all models and software tools run on the ITWM HPC cluster beehive.
- All models and software tools that are part of a workflow step are encapsulated within an individual OCI (Open Container Initiative⁸) software container, respectively.
- The program interface of each software tool / container is standardized by a convention, which defines bash scripts that handles program initialization, parallel execution, and post processing.
- Model parameters and initial conditions are given in `JSON` file format
- Evaluation results are serialized to files, which can be interpreted by the Runtime environment of the simulation platform, which is implemented in `Python 3`.

Figure 4 shows the use of OCI software containers to implement and to execute the workflow steps shown in Figure 3 by means of container runtime implementations like `Podman` or `Docker`. We decided to use the implementation of `Podman` as basis for containerization, as it has been considered to provide the most popular container format, yet. As one contribution of Upwards is to provide the integration system with all components as Open Accessible Framework, we specified a concrete format each container must follow to be used in Upwards, which means to be integrated within the workflow.

Figure 4 Upward's containerized wind park simulation workflow

⁸ <https://opencontainers.org/>

The execution of simulators within this workflow at the HPC cluster Beehive was developed in Task 6.3 on behalf of multiple software systems. Figure 5 lists involved software systems and summarizes a generalized view of interaction.

Figure 5: Eco system of Upwards HPC simulation platform

3.1. Hardware – The HPC Cluster Beehive

The HPC cluster Beehive provides the basic hardware infrastructure of Upward's runtime environment platform. Here is a small overview about the resources provided by ITWM Beehive:

Server Vendor: Dell

48x MPI compute node (Dell PowerEdge M640):

- dual Intel Xeon Gold 6132
- 28 CPU cores per node
- 192 GB RAM
- 480 GB SSD
- 2x Gigabit Ethernet
- FDR Infiniband

108x MPI compute node (Dell PowerEdge C6420):

- dual Intel Xeon Gold 6240R
- 48 CPU cores per node

- 384 GB RAM (8 GB RAM per core)
- 480 GB SSD
- 10 Gigabit Ethernet
- HDR100 Infiniband

13x SMP compute nodes (Dell PowerEdge):

- dual Intel Xeon CPUs, 16 -36 CPU cores total
- 256 -768 GB RAM
- 300 - 500 GB HDD
- 2x Gigabit Ethernet
- FDR Infiniband

Storage System

- 12 storage servers (Dell PowerEdge R720xd):
- 2x 600 GB SATA SSD (for meta data)
- 24x 6 TB SAS HDD (for object data)
- 10 Gigabit Ethernet
- FDR Infiniband

3.2. Software - Containerization

“[...] Like a normal Linux program, containers really have two states - rest and running. When at rest, a container is a file (or set of files) that is saved on disk. This is referred to as a Container Image or Container Repository. When you type the command to start a container, the Container Engine unpacks the required files and meta-data, then hands them off to the the Linux kernel. Starting a container is very similar to starting a normal Linux process and requires making an API call to the Linux kernel. This API call typically initiates extra isolation and mounts a copy of the files that were in the container image. Once running, Containers are just a Linux process. The process for starting containers, as well as the image format on disk, are defined and governed by standards.

There are several competing Container Image formats (Docker, Appc, LXD), but the industry is moving forward with a standard governed under the Open Container Initiative - sometimes referred to simply as Open Containers or the OCI. The scope of the OCI includes a Container Image Format Specification, which defines the on-disk format for container images as well as the meta-data which defines things like hardware architecture and the operating system (Linux, Windows, etc.). An industry wide container image format enables ecosystems of software to flourish - different individual contributors, projects, and vendors are able to build images and tooling, which are interoperable. Users want interoperability between tools for signing, scanning, building, running, moving and managing container images. [...] Tools which target the OCI Container Image Format Specification and Container Runtime Specification ensure portability between a broad ecosystem of container platforms, container engines, and supporting tools across cloud providers and on-premise architectures. (https://developers.redhat.com/blog/2018/02/22/container-terminology-practical-introduction#containers_101)”

We provide container images to Upwards partners in the version control system GITLAB, which is hosted by Fraunhofer ITWM⁹ (see Figure 6). Each software applications in Upwards, such as WRF, OPENFOAM, STAR-CCM+, SAMSEF is encapsulated separately in a container image, which finally transforms the software to a standalone micro service, that partners can easily package and deliver as container images. In addition, the release version of each software can be easily exchanged, respectively.

Figure 6: Upwards container image registry

⁹ https://gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de/sys/upwards/container_registry

The following CLI command pulls a container image that encapsulates the noise simulation:

```
podman pull gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de:4567/sys/upwards/mynoise:v4.0
```

A so-called `Dockerfile` defines the content of an executable container image. Figure 7 shows an example `Dockerfile` that encapsulates `OPENFOAM`. If possible, build routines used inside the `Dockerfile` should request open-sources binaries and public data from Web resources. Closed source binaries and data are provided in Gitlab, which is only accessible by partners of the Upwards consortium agreement, to enables these to access and build containers with closed source proprietary software systems such as `STAR-CCM+` or `SAMCEF`. Required license files and network addresses of respective license servers must be configurable within the `Dockerfile`.


```

1 # Start from the official Ubuntu Bionic (18.04 LTS) image
2 FROM ubuntu:bionic
3
4 # Install any extra things we might need
5 RUN apt-get update \
6     && apt-get install -y \
7         vim \
8         ssh \
9         make \
10        sudo \
11        wget \
12        software-properties-common ;\
13        rm -rf /var/lib/apt/lists/*
14
15 # Create a new user called foam
16 RUN useradd --user-group --create-home --shell /bin/bash foam ;\
17     echo "foam ALL=(ALL) NOPASSWD:ALL" >> /etc/sudoers
18
19 # Install OpenFOAM v6 (without ParaView)
20 # including configuring for use by user=foam
21 # plus an extra environment variable to make OpenMPI play nice
22 RUN sh -c "wget -O - http://dl.openfoam.org/gpg.key | apt-key add -" ;\
23     add-apt-repository http://dl.openfoam.org/ubuntu ;\
24     apt-get update ;\
25     apt-get install -y --no-install-recommends openfoam6 ;\
26     rm -rf /var/lib/apt/lists/* ;\
27     echo "source /opt/openfoam6/etc/bashrc" >> ~foam/.bashrc ;\
28     echo "export OMPI_MCA_btl_vader_single_copy_mechanism=none" >> ~foam/.bashrc
29
30 # Copy binaries of OffwindModel and OffwindSolver
31 ADD linux64GccDPInt320pt /opt/openfoam6/platforms/linux64GccDPInt320pt
32
33 #ADD applications /opt/openfoam6/applications
34 #ADD applications/solvers/windenergy/OffwindSolver/OffwindModels /opt/openfoam6/src/OffwindModels
35 #RUN /bin/bash -c "source /opt/openfoam6/etc/bashrc ;\
36 # cd /opt/openfoam6/src/OffwindModels;\
37 # wmake libso"
38 #RUN /bin/bash -c "source /opt/openfoam6/etc/bashrc ;\
39 # cd /opt/openfoam6/applications/solvers/windenergy/OffwindSolver;\
40 # wmake libso"
41
42 # set the default container user to foam
43 USER foam

```

Figure 7: Example Dockerfile of the container that encapsulates OPENFOAM

It is imported to point out that `podman` is used to start rootless containers. Hence, users execute containers by means of standard user privileges. For security reasons, root privileges are restricted to administrative routines. `Podman` realizes these rootless containers by using the `linux` kernel feature of sub user ids, that way that all container resources are mapped to an existing user on host level.

3.3. Software – HPC with containers

The Upwards HPC Integrated Simulation Environment is implemented by executing OCI containers using Podman V3 within an MPI¹⁰ (message passing interface) environment. “Podman (the POD MANager) is a tool for managing containers and images, volumes mounted into those containers, and pods made from groups of containers. Podman is based on libpod, a library for container lifecycle management that is also contained in this repository. The libpod library provides APIs for managing containers, pods, container images, and volumes.”¹¹

We rely the implementation on Podman and not on Singularity¹², which is a container runtime implementation that has been designed to execute containers in HPC environments. The main reason behind this design decision was that due to IP rights the Upwards partners package and deliver the container images on their own. Hence, it was not possible for ITWM developers to change or adapt the source code of these systems. Unfortunately, the software Singularity was not available on their infrastructures. The IT efforts to add it was estimated as too high as the software alternative Docker was known and already been in use. A conversion between OCI container images built by the Docker software to Singularity container images was tested (with a container image that encapsulates OpenFoam), unfortunately without success. The container images used in Upwards embed software systems that are built on two different MPI distributions, namely Open MPI¹³ and MPICH¹⁴.

Distributing simulation jobs with Open MPI

In WRF and OpenFoam, Open MPI is used to implement a star-based communication topology, in which computing processes are forked in count of requested numbers of cores. The simplified pattern of such a call is described in Figure 8:

```
#####
# ---Setup path to container image registry
#####
path_auth=~/.config/containers/auth.json
domain_repo=gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de:4567
image_name=mywrf:v6

#####
# ---Setup required open mpi version
#####
module add p/sys/openmpi-x86_64/1.10.7
dir_mpi=/tmp/podman-mpirun-$USER

#####
# ---Start WRF process
#####
mpirun -display-map -np <number of processes>
--mca orte_tmpdir_base $dir_mpi \
```

¹⁰ <https://www.mpi-forum.org/>

¹¹ <https://github.com/containers/podman>

¹² <https://github.com/apptainer/singularity>

¹³ <https://www.open-mpi.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.mpich.org/>

```
podman run --env-host --env-file=$data_root_folder/container.env --authfile $path_auth --rm \
-v $dir_mpi:$dir_mpi \
-v $sim_data_dir/data:/home/wrf/data \
-v $sim_data_dir/scripts:/home/wrf/scripts \
-v $sim_data_dir/.cdsapirc:/home/wrf/.cdsapirc \
-v $sim_data_dir/conf:/home/wrf/conf \
-v /dev/infiniband:/dev/infiniband \
-v $sim_data_dir:/home/wrf \
-w /home/wrf/data/run -u $UID:$gid --userns=keep-id --net=host --pid=host --ipc=host
$domain_repo/sys/upwards/$image_name /home/wrf/data/run/wrf.exe
```

Figure 8: HPC call of the WRF process

The Open MPI process `mpirun` is started at the host node environment. The passed command `podman` starts to pull the referenced container image from the registry on each host node. The `WRF` binary is finally executed from within the started container environment. Hence, for each number of processes, the `WRF` container is started individually on involved hosts. The references to available host nodes are managed by the resource manager `slurm`¹⁵. The available host names are listed in an environment variable, which was initialized when starting the `slurm` session. These environment variables are ingested into the container environments, respectively.

Distributing simulation jobs by MPICH

In `STARCCM+`, which is a software system that is used within noise and fluid-structure interaction simulations, the `MPI` distribution `MPICH` is used in a master-slave topology. Here, on a master node a process manager called `hydra` spawns tasks to slave processes on slave nodes. The spawning as such is implemented by opening remote `SSH` sessions to slave nodes and starting a remote process.

3.4. Storage management in containerized HPC environments

As shown in Figure 5, the storage management in Upwards integrated simulation platform is divided into different levels at ITWM infrastructure:

1. **local storage on node level:** This storage consists of local HDD devices of each node's server rack. It is accessible by sub users from within container runtimes and used to store the container images with short-term lifespan.
2. **network storage based on BeeGFS¹⁶ on cluster level:** These storage servers are formatted by the file system BeeGFS, which is designed to perform in HPC workloads. It is accessible by sub users from within container runtimes. Stored data is available for all cluster nodes. Here, input data and intermediate output data as well as configuration data is stored with mid-term lifespan.
3. **network storage based on NFS on platform level:** These large storage servers are managed as NFS. Hence, data is not accessible by sub users from within container runtimes, as the NFS server is not configured to resolve sub user ids.

Within a workflow runtime of a simulation run, the storage management follows a defined process:

1. Pull project data with simulation configuration from Gitlab to storage on platform level.
2. Copy project data to storage on cluster level.

¹⁵ <https://slurm.schedmd.com/>

¹⁶ <https://www.beegfs.io/>

3. Pull container images from Gitlab to storage on node level.
4. Start container by linking shared volumes from project directory on cluster level to container runtime on node level.
5. Copy results from cluster level to project directory on platform level.
6. Release data on node level.

During the project duration of Upwards project, general data resources (multiple GB) such as terrain data or historic weather data remain on cluster level to avoid long lasting copy jobs.

3.5. License management for commercial on-premise software

Especially the software stack from Siemens uses commercial software. For this purpose, required research licenses have been deployed to running license servers that handle different types (e.g., FlexLM, OLicense). The path to these license servers is configured and passed to container environments by using environment variables, such as it can be seen below:

```
CDLMD_LICENSE_FILE=27040@lls1.itwm.fhg.de
```

3.6. Program interface

To start a simulation within the HPC integrated simulation platform the program interface is used which was defined in D6.1. The program interface of each container provides a shell command called `runAll.sh` or `host.run.sh`. The script manages following tasks:

1. Set path to project directory on platform level
2. Set correct working directories on cluster and node level
3. Set correct paths to container image registry
4. Set correct environment paths to required OpenMPI binary version (OpenFoam is compiled with `openmpi 2.1.1`, WRF is compiled with `openmpi 1.10.7`)
5. Copy project data from platform level to cluster level
6. Pull container images to all nodes
7. Configure containers with required volumes, hardware access, network configuration and environment variables
8. Start preprocessing processes
9. Start simulation process
10. Start post processing postprocesses
11. Copy simulated result data from cluster level to platform level
12. Cleanup

Figure 9 shows the `runAll.sh` script that executes a simulation of the WRF container. This script takes input data from files and writes simulation results into files. These files are stored at the host system and mounted into the container runtime.

```
#!/bin/bash

data_root_folder=/s/dep/sys/w/upwards/gitlab/upwards/case_studies/lillgrund-
vindpark/atmosphere/lillgrund
```

```
sim_name=lillgrund
sim_dir=/scratch/upwards

# Generate paths / directories for podman container and simulation results.
# Pattern for folders: day-month-year_<4-character-uuid>
sim_start=$(date +"%d-%m-%Y")
sim_data_dir=$sim_dir/atmosphere/$sim_name/"$sim_start"_
sim_results_dir=$data_root_folder/sim_output/"$sim_start"_

# Use first 4 characters of uuid to match simulation with result folder names. (Arbitrary choice
to keep it readable.)
sim_uuid=$(cat /proc/sys/kernel/random/uuid | cut -c 1-4)
while [ -d "$sim_data_dir$sim_data_num/" ] || [ -d "$sim_results_dir$sim_num/" ]; do
    sim_uuid=$(cat /proc/sys/kernel/random/uuid | cut -c 1-4)
done

sim_data_dir=$sim_data_dir$sim_uuid
mkdir -p $sim_data_dir
echo "Generating simulation data at:" $sim_data_dir

sim_results_dir=$sim_results_dir$sim_uuid
mkdir -p $sim_results_dir
echo "Writing simulation data to:" $sim_results_dir

dir_mpi=/tmp/podman-mpirun-$USER
path_auth=~/.config/containers/auth.json
domain_repo=gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de:4567
image_name=mywrf:v6
gid=$(id -g $USER)

export MODULEPATH=$MODULEPATH:/p/sys/soft/etc/
export TMPDIR=/var/tmp

module add p/sys/openmpi-x86_64/1.10.7

mkdir -p $sim_data_dir/output
mkdir -p $sim_data_dir/data
#cp -vr $data_root_folder $sim_dir/
cp -r $data_root_folder/scripts $sim_data_dir
cp -r $data_root_folder/conf $sim_data_dir
cp -r $data_root_folder/*.sh $sim_data_dir
cp -r $data_root_folder/.cdsapirc $sim_data_dir

cd $sim_data_dir

#####
# ---PREPROCESSING SECTION -- SERIAL (ALL PYTHON SCRIPTS)
#####
echo "Preprocessing (serial / python)"
podman run --authfile $path_auth --rm \
```

```

-v $sim_data_dir:/home/wrf/.local \
-v $sim_data_dir/data:/home/wrf/data \
-v $sim_data_dir/scripts:/home/wrf/scripts \
-v $sim_data_dir/container.pre.sh:/home/wrf/container.pre.sh \
-v $sim_data_dir/.cdsapirc:/home/wrf/.cdsapirc \
-v $sim_data_dir/output:/home/wrf/.saalem_cache \
-v $sim_data_dir/output:/home/wrf/.cache \
-v $sim_data_dir/conf:/home/wrf/conf \
-w /home/wrf -u $UID:$gid --userns=keep-id --net=host --pid=host --ipc=host
$domain_repo/sys/upwards/$image_name ./container.pre.sh

#####
# ---SIMULATION SECTION -- SERIAL
#####
echo "Simulation (serial)"
podman run --authfile $path_auth --rm \
-v $sim_data_dir:/home/wrf/.local \
-v $sim_data_dir/data:/home/wrf/data \
-v $sim_data_dir/scripts:/home/wrf/scripts \
-v $sim_data_dir/.cdsapirc:/home/wrf/.cdsapirc \
-v $sim_data_dir/conf:/home/wrf/conf \
-w /home/wrf/data/run -u $UID:$gid --userns=keep-id --net=host --pid=host --ipc=host
$domain_repo/sys/upwards/$image_name /home/wrf/data/run/real.exe

#####
# ---SIMULATION SECTION -- PARALLEL
#####
echo "Simulation (parallel)"
mpirun -display-map -np 48
--mca btl "openib,tcp,vader,self" \
--mca btl_tcp_if_include br0 \
--mca orte_tmpdir_base $dir_mpi \
podman run --env-host --env-file=$data_root_folder/container.env --authfile $path_auth --rm \
-v $sim_data_dir:/home/wrf/.local \
-v $dir_mpi:$dir_mpi \
-v $sim_data_dir/data:/home/wrf/data \
-v $sim_data_dir/scripts:/home/wrf/scripts \
-v $sim_data_dir/conf:/home/wrf/conf \
-v /dev/infiniband:/dev/infiniband \
-v $sim_data_dir:/home/wrf \
-w /home/wrf/data/run -u $UID:$gid --userns=keep-id --net=host --pid=host --ipc=host
$domain_repo/sys/upwards/$image_name /home/wrf/data/run/wrf.exe
#if [ $? -ne 0 ]; then echo "ERROR- wrf.exe has failed "; exit 3; fi

#####
# ---POSTPROCESSING SECTION -- SERIAL (ALL PYTHON SCRIPTS)
#####
echo "Postprocessing (serial / python)"
podman run --authfile $path_auth --rm
-v $sim_data_dir:/home/wrf/.local \

```

```

-v $sim_data_dir/data:/home/wrf/data \
-v $sim_data_dir/scripts:/home/wrf/scripts \
-v $sim_data_dir/container.post.sh:/home/wrf/container.post.sh \
-v $sim_data_dir/conf:/home/wrf/conf \
-w /home/wrf -u $UID:$gid --users=keep-id --net=host --pid=host --ipc=host
$domain_repo/sys/upwards/$image_name ./container.post.sh
# Copy simulation results from scratch disk to simulation result folder.
cp -R $sim_data_dir/output $sim_results_dir

```

Figure 9: Example program interface of the WRF container

The execution of a container is triggered by using the container API. Inside the Linux machine, it is possible to call this container API by using a shell command called `podman`. The example presented in Figure 10 shows such a basic command line call that executes of the WRF container.

<code>podman run</code>	<i>Request the container API by using the command shell program "podman".</i>
<code>--rm</code>	<i>Close container runtime after execution.</i>
<code>-v \$sim_data_dir/data:/home/wrf/data</code>	<i>Mount a folder from host system on cluster level as volume within the container runtime</i>
<code>-v /dev/infiniband:/dev/infiniband</code>	<i>Mount a local infiniband device from host system as volume within the container runtime</i>
<code>-v \$sim_data_dir/container.post.sh:/home/wrf/container.post.sh</code>	<i>Mount a shell command into the container runtime.</i>
<code>-w /home/wrf</code>	<i>Set the working directory within the container runtime</i>
<code>mywrf:v6</code>	<i>Name of the container image</i>
<code>/bin/bash -c "./container.post.sh "</code>	<i>Command to execute within the container runtime.</i>

Figure 10: Executing the WRF container

Finally, the software conventions of Upwards can be summarized as follows:

1. Each workflow step is represented as software container.
2. The content of structure of a software container is described by the `Dockerfile`.
3. A software container is executed by shell scripts

This allows users to exchange each software system by other implementations or different external software in the future, in principle.

3.7. Simulation models and systems

The partners of the Upwards consortium delivered their software systems of the workflow steps in form of HPC enabled software containers. This resembles the objective of milestone MS12 (HPC Integrated simulator), reached in March 2022. All necessary software systems being involved within a workflow step have been containerized. The container images and respective `Dockerfiles` are managed in a container image registry in `Gitlab`. Figure 11 lists the current container images.

Workflow step	Encapsulated software	Container image
atmospheric model (WP2)	WRF	gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de:4567/sys/upwards/mywrf
park model (WP2)	OPENFOAM	gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de:4567/sys/upwards/myopenfoam
fluid-structure interaction analysis (WP3,5)	STAR-CCM+, SAMSEF	gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de:4567/sys/upwards/mecano-star
noise propagation (WP4)	STAR-CCM+	gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de:4567/sys/upwards/mynoise

Figure 11: Overview of container images in Upwards

3.8. Data exchange interface

The data exchange interface defines the data format of initial conditions, model parameters, and simulation results. A convention in Upwards is that all input parameters are serialized in `JSON` notation in a plain text file. These files can be modified outside containers and ingested into container runtimes as volumes. Figure 12 shows an example content of the input parameter file in `JSON` notation. The atmospheric model calculates the wind conditions in atmosphere scale within the area of the wind park. Therefore, it requires initial conditions about the latitude and longitude coordinates of the geo position of the park, the height of the domain to serialize an inlet layer for the park model and the date.

```
{
  "wind_farm_location": {
    "latitude" : [55.508556],
    "longitude" : [12.762694],
    "height" : [65]
  },
  "rotor_diameter" : 93,
  "dateLimits" : ["2018-10-08 00:00", "2018-10-09 00:00"],
  "namelist_template_wps" : "namelist.wps.M_size",
  "namelist_template_input" : "namelist.input.M_size",
  "era5_data_frequency" : 180,
  "wrf_output_frequency" : 10,
  "what_to_do" : {
    "do_era5_download" : true,
    "do_vtk_output" : true,
    "do_noise_output" : true
  }
}
```

Figure 12: Input parameter of atmospheric model in `JSON` notation

```

{
# WT park info
"WT": { # WT park name
  "WT1": { # WT name
    "turbineType": "SWT_2.3MW", # WT type, should in list of WT below
    "position": [5.7290583, 58.6487743], # WT position in WGS coordinates (lon, lat)
    "yaw": "calculated", # yaw angle "calculated" or value
    "rpm": "calculated", # rotational speed "calculated" or value
    "pitch": "calculated", # blade pitch angle "calculated" or value
    "UInduced": "calculated" # induced velocity over the
  },
  "WT2": { # Additional WT
  },
},
# flow files
"turbines_flow": "WRF", # takes the input from WRF or OpenFoam
# file for extracting turbines flow data
"turbines_flow_file": "/home/noise/wrfoutput/wrfout_noise_d05_2018-06-12_11_00.nc",
"far_field": "False", # if far-field noise propagation
# atmospheric flow file for far-field propagation
"acoustic_flow_file": "/home/noise/wrfoutput/wrfout_noise_d05_2018-06-12_11_00.nc",
# output grid
"observers":
{
  "origin": [5.7379504, 58.6440331], # center in WGS coordinates (lon, lat)
  "extent": [3000.0, 3000.0], # domain extent in meters in x/y directions
  "n_pts": [151, 151] # number of points in x/y directions
},
# definition of wind turbine info
"turbinesInfo":
{
  "SWT_2.3MW": { # WT type
    "geom_file": "/home/noise/data/swt2.3MW-93.stl", # blade geometry file
    "pitch": -3.0, # reference pitch angle to set geometry to zero pitch
    # WT operating curves wind speed vs. rpm vs. pitch
    "operating_curves": "/home/noise/data/swt2.3MW-93_operating_param.json",
    "B": 3, # number of blades
    "height": 80.0, # mast height
    "radialClip": [10.0, 50.0] # reduce blade radius range for acoustic predictions
  }
},
# acoustic parameters - overwriting defaults parameters
"batmanpyParams": {
  "steps": ["geom", "cut", "cfd", "flow", "amiet"], # steps to execute
  "nstrips": 5, # number of radial cuts along span
  "cfd_cfd_exec": "starccm+", # starccm+ solve command + options
  "cfd_inlet_type": "interpUniform", # use uniform flow conditions upstream of WT
  "cfd_maxIterSteps": 5000, # maximum number of iterations for starccm
  "cfd_nprocs": 48, # number of proc for starccm computations
  "cfd_blockGrow" : 1.06, # cell to cell ratio

```

```

"cfld_yplus": 1.0, # wall y+
"cfld_prismLayer": 40, # number of BL cells
"cfld_geomRepr": "polyline", # representation of surface
"flow_inlet_type": "interpUniform", # use uniform flow conditions upstream of WT
"flow_side": ["ss", "ps"], # sides for TE noise evaluation
"flow_wp_model": ["Lee", "GoodyDeltaStarPowerLaw"], # wall pressure models
"flow_patch": "Body 2", # flow patch name
"amiet_int_npts": 12, # number of integration points
"amiet_source_export": "False", # export source for far-field propagation
"save_file": "observer_grid.sc_h5",
"save_info": ["list"]
}
}

```

Figure 13: Input config for noise simulation

Figure 13 shows a more complex input configuration for the container that encapsulates noise simulations.

4. How to generate simulation results

Figure 14 summarizes the workflow, which can now be executed on the HPC cluster *Beehive* to generate simulation results. All boxes represent containers, which can be executed on multiple cores in parallel.

Figure 14 Data generating workflow

Based on the complexity of the simulation one can configure the count of required cores when starting a cluster session by using the software *slurm* and a convenient script of ITWM's IT getnode:

```

[adrian@v110sys01 ~]$ ssh beehive
+-----+

Welcome to the Beehive cluster!

This host is running OracleLinux 8.5
https://cluster.itwm.fraunhofer.de/ClusterBeehiveEL8

Check the cluster website for news and documentation:
https://cluster.itwm.fraunhofer.de

+-----+
Activate the web console with: systemctl enable --now cockpit.socket

```

```

Last login: Mon Mar  7 09:09:46 2022 from 10.136.23.16
Next scheduled cluster maintenance: 2022-03-10 09:00:00
[adrian@login1 ~]$ getnode --help
getnode: reserve cluster node(s) for exclusive use
version 3.0 (2021-08)

Usage: getnode [<options>] [<srun options>]

Options:
    -n --ntasks <cores>    request CPU cores (default: 8)
    -t --time <hours>      reserve for specified time

    --timeout <hours>      abort pending job after
                           specified waiting time in queue
    --abort <time> abort pending job at this time
                           (default: "today 18:00")

    --debug
    -h --help

[adrian@login1 ~]$ getnode -n 48 -t 12
This cluster job will terminate on Wed Mar  9 22:43:06 CET 2022
[adrian@node009 ~]$ cd /s/dep/sys/w/upwards/gitlab/upwards/case_studies/lillgrund-
vindpark/atmosphere/lillgrund
[adrian@node009 lillgrund]$ ls
conf          container.post.sh  copy_geog.sh  host.run.sh  sim_output
container.env  container.pre.sh  scripts
[adrian@node009 lillgrund]$ ./host.run.sh

```

Figure 15: Shell transcript which starts a parallel atmospheric simulation based on 48 cores

In WP6 we also developed a CLI wrapping CLI tool which simplifies the start of simulations at the Beehive cluster (see Figure 16).

```

#-----#
# The Upwards Beehive CLI (ubee) simplifies WRF and OpenFOAM simulations on the Beehive cluster. #
#-----#

Usage: ubee [options] wrf <path_to_case_study>
       ubee [options] openfoam <path_to_case_study>
       ubee [options] noise <path_to_case_study> <path_to_noise_data>

NOTE: Execute this script in conjunction with the getnode command.
In case docker containers cannot be pulled from the container registry
using podman-config on a Beehive cluster node is likely fix.

Be sure to set the correct MPI version of your specific WRF or OpenFOAM container
has been compiled against!

Options: -h          Print this Help.
         -c <number_cores> Set number of cores. (Default in ubee-config)
         -s <location> Set simulation directory. (Default in ubee-config)
         -n <name> Set simulation name.
         -mpi <version> Set OpenMPI version (Default in ubee-config)
         -r <registry> Set location of container registry. (Default in ubee-config)
         -i <image> Set name of image to pull from container registry. (Default in ubee-config)

```

Figure 16: Upwards CLI interface for Beehive executions (UBEE)

5. Conclusions

In this report, we documented the demonstrator of the HPC integrated simulation, which was developed in Task 6.3 and installed at the ITWM HPC cluster *Beehive*. This documentation provides explanation to all components used to implement this HPC integrated simulation platform. It explained the concept of the extended workflow of D6.1 underpinning the concept of Upwards to combine physical simulation systems.

Furthermore, this report describes the technical foundations to encapsulate used simulation systems in HPC enabled software containers. It presents conventions made to create standard application interfaces to initialize and run simulations in parallel on multiple cores and data exchange interfaces between involved systems.

The benefit of adding more cores to a simulation is shown in Figure 17. We executed the same WRF simulation on Hogjaeren twice with different count of cores (48 cores and 96 cores). Doubling the number of cores decreases simulation time by 35%.

Figure 17 Simulation times in minutes for two WRF simulations using different number of cores.

Partners of the Upwards consortium access the container images by using the Gitlab collaboration platform hosted by Fraunhofer ITWM (<https://gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de/sys/upwards>).

The Container runtime `podman`¹⁷ is still under development. We recommend maintaining the HPC integrated simulation platform with upcoming releases of `podman` as we expect an increasing amount of support to execute rootless containers in HPC clusters.

¹⁷ <https://podman.io/releases/>